

Active Learning, choosing the type of Resource according to Learning Style

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Abstract

The diversity of learning styles refers to the individuals' approach when it comes to receiving information. It can be described by the various ways individuals prefer to acquire and process information. Different educational resources have an impact on how students learn. This study examines how different types of resources can affect student learning. We're especially interested in understanding how visual, auditory, and written styles of learning are impacted. The idea is to make the learner an active participant in his learning by choosing the type of resource best suited to their preferred learning style. We applied a case study on 60 students studying the computer engineering diploma at the Esprit School of Engineering. The paper concludes with a discussion of how teaching based on different learning styles could be introduced into the school and the implications for teaching and assessment.

Keywords: Learning styles; Educational resources; Active learner; Computer engineering.

1 Introduction

Active learning is a paradigm shift in education that puts learners at the centre of the learning process. By actively engaging with course material, collaborating with peers and applying their knowledge to real-world situations, individuals develop the critical thinking skills, creativity and resilience needed to thrive in a changing world. Integrating active learning strategies tailored to different learning styles can increase the effectiveness of educational interventions.

The learner plays a central role in the learning process. In addition to the traditional role of the teacher, the learner is also a major player in his or her own acquisition of knowledge and skills. Understanding the learner's role in learning is essential to designing effective and stimulating learning environments (Liang et al., 2023).

Learners have different preferences about how they absorb information. Some learn best through hands-on, experiential activities, while others prefer verbal explanations or visual aids. By identifying each student's learning style, teachers can adapt their teaching methods to meet individual needs, promoting deeper understanding and better retention (Moneva et al., 2020).

The importance of learning style in a learner's education lies in its ability to influence the way an individual acquires, processes and retains information. Understanding learning styles enables educators to design teaching strategies that are appropriate for each learner, leading to better retention, greater motivation and a more positive learning experience. When learners are exposed to teaching methods that match their preferred style, they are more likely to actively engage in the learning process. This can increase their intrinsic motivation by building confidence in their abilities and creating a positive and stimulating learning environment (CB, 2022).

Learning style is the way in which each learner begins to concentrate on, process, absorb, and retain new and difficult information (Dunn and Burke, 2005). The interaction of these elements occurs differently in everyone. Therefore, it is necessary to determine what is most likely to trigger each student's concentration, how to maintain it, and how to respond to his or her natural processing style to produce long term memory and

retention. To reveal these natural tendencies and styles, it is important to use a comprehensive model of learning style that identifies each individual's strengths and preferences across the full spectrum of physiological, sociological, psychological, emotional, and environmental elements. (Pashler et al., 2009).

The learning styles will certainly differ among students in the classroom; Dunn and Dunn said that teachers should try to make changes in their classroom that will be beneficial to every learning style. Some of these changes include room redesign, the development of small-group techniques, and the development of Contract Activity Packages. Redesigning the classroom involves locating dividers that can be used to arrange the room creatively, clearing the floor area, and incorporating student thoughts and ideas into the design of the classroom (Dunn et al., 1979).

Over the years several theories and types of learning style models have been developed. The learning style has several models pioneered by some of the people figures. Among the models of learning styles are such as Dunn and Dunn learning style model, Kolb learning style model, Felder Silverman learning style model, VAK learning style model, Visual, Audio, 'Read and Write' and Kinesthetic (VARK) learning style model, Honey and Mumford learning style model, Selmes learning style model and so on. (Kannan et al., 2011).

In comparison to other learning modes, the VARK model is more sophisticated and provides more desirable outcomes. Its purpose is to examine the relationship between the mind and linguistics in an individual's behaviour (Hawk et al., 2007). The VARK learning style model, introduced by Fleming, is a questionnaire that identifies a person's sensory modality preference when learning. This model classifies students into four different learning modes: visual (V), auditory (or Aural)(A), read/write (R) and kinesthetic (K).

While there are several tools to study learning styles of students, the visual-aural-read/write-kinesthetic (VARK) questionnaire is a simple, freely available, easy to administer tool that encourages students to describe their behavior in a manner they can identify with and accept. The aim is to understand the preferred sensory modality (or modalities) of students for learning. (Urval et al., 2014).

The aim of this paper is to explore how we used the VARK model to identify how students prefer to learn in different activities. Through our own experience, we have gained valuable insights into the impact of this approach on learners.

2 Methodology

2.1 Description of the module

It is a three-credit module which consists of an integrated course entitled service-oriented architecture SOA.

It is taught during the first semester of each academic year. The former is extended for 7 weeks, and 9 hours asynchronous activities. This module is intended for 2nd year Computer Engineering whose number is approximately 570 divided into 9 specialities. In software engineering, service-oriented architecture (SOA) is an architectural style that focuses on discrete services instead of a monolithic design. Students are required to understand this architectural style and implement a REST API in order to meet the requirements of their final client. Teachers prepare a Moodle space related to this module where learners can find all the necessary tools and resources. Teachers upload assignments for students to complete and add a discussion forum for further interaction in addition to other useful links.

2.2 Description of the approach

This section is a detailed description of the strategy we have in place to put our experience into practice.

This task involved four steps:

- (a) preparing the VARK questionnaire (in Google Forms)
- (b) sending the form's link to be completed by learner
- (c) analysing the results of the questionnaire
- (d) Identify the learning style of each individual learner to determine what forms of evidence would be needed to justify basing pedagogical choices on material resource of students' learning styles

The module average is calculated as follows: Average = 20% Continuous Monitoring (CM) + 80% Final Examen

In this experience, we choose two different activities and we contribute the score in CM. There were two activities:

1. The first activity is based on an individual exercise for which we have (as a teacher) provided teaching resources (statements, lessons, explanations, etc.) according to the learning style of each student, as identified during the analysis of the completed forms.
2. The second activity is a team activity. Normally, teams are formed at random, but this time we selected teams based on learning style results. Students with similar learning styles are grouped into teams of 5 or 6 students.

The first activity is on chapter 2 introduction and discussion of the engineering SOA architecture and we have provided an exercise to do and resources to consult to give us an explanatory affinity.

The second activity is based on chapter 3 introduction and discussion of the engineering REST architecture, and is based on a problem-based learning (PBL). We (as a teacher) have provided all the necessary resources to consult and to give us an explanatory affinity with executable code according to the given statement. https://orbi.uliege.be/bitstream/2268/296618/1/1998_Leclercq_Van_der_Vleuten_PBL_PPUQ_Chap8.pdf

VARK Model in Teaching use 4 types of learning style as shown in the figure below:

Figure 1. VARK Learning Styles

1. One style of learning is visual. People whose dominant learning styles revolve around visual stimulation. They strongly prefer to process and understand information using visual aids like charts, diagrams, graphs, pictures and videos. (Kumah et al., 2022). For this category, we provided the resources in the form of capsules (videos) and pictures.
2. For auditory learners, listening is the preferred method of learning. They tend to absorb and retain information presented in an auditory format more effectively. This is why participation in group lessons, exercises and discussions is so important to the learning process. (Kumah et al., 2022) For the auditory learning style, we provided all the resources in the form of audio (recorded lectures and podcasts (mp4)).

3. For reading/writing learners (or Literate learners), also known as oral language learners, prefer to learn through the written word and text-based materials. They have an excellent affinity for reading, writing and using written information. (Kumah et al., 2022)
For the reading/writing learning style, we provided all the resources in the form of documents (books, article, word, pdf, paper and online resources)
4. Kinesthetic learners can be identified using a number of observable characteristics. These learners tend to be very active and prefer hands-on experience. They find it difficult to stand still for long periods and tend to move around frequently. Kinesthetic learners also have a strong inner voice of their own body and are able to make physical gestures and movements when thinking and speaking. (Kumah et al., 2022)
For the kinesthetics learning style, we provided all the resources in the form of role-playing, experiments, and simulation.

In this part, we had a difficulty in preparing resources according to learning style preferences. It was essential to research the preference of each style before preparing the resources. All the resources were shared using the standard drive tool.

This study was conducted at the beginning of the first semester of the 2023/2024 academic year. Quantitative measures were used. We only carried out our experiment on two classes, and around 60 students took part in our survey. Students were asked for feedback using paper surveys. The survey was anonymous. We received 56 responses from 60 registered students. This represents a participation rate of approximately 93%. The ages of participants range from 21 to 25 with the age of 22 approximately.

3 Results

3.1 Scholar Results

We only carried out our experiment on two classes (60 students). For data collection, the VARK questionnaire was adopted and used. Descriptively, it was noted that 24(40%) of the participants prefer Visual learning ,23 (38%) are Kinesthetic learning ,7(12%) prefer Auditory learning , and 6(10%) prefer Reading/Writing learning style. Preferred student's learning style are shown in [Fig. 2](#).

Figure 2. Learning styles by percent

On the other hand, we have noticed that the distribution of preferences according to gender is as follows in Table 1

Table 1. Male and Female Students' Learning Styles.

Gender/Learning Styles	Number	Auditory	Visual	Reading/Writing	Kinesthetic
Male	24 (40%)	8,03%	24,8%	5,30%	64,44%
Female	36 (60%)	12,54%	75,20%	9,80%	35,56%

The number of students per interval of their averages (CM) shown in Fig. 3. This figure shows that about 97% of the students validated their activities. Compared to the traditional method of the previous year, this percentage is more interesting.

Figure 3. Final Continuous Monitoring Average

Table 2. Results of participations.

Activity	First Activity (Individual)	Second Activity (Group)
Download resources	87%	75%
Workshop submission on Moodle	97%	93%
Students who validate the workshop	97%	93%

Table 2 shows that 97% completed the first activity, 93% submitted the second activity. Table 2 also shows the number of students who download their resources. In the second activity, we had the observation that only one or two learners had downloaded the resources for the whole team.

It shows also the number of students that validated their workshop (activity 1 and 2) and they obtained at least 10/20. Finally, 97% of students validated the first activity, 93% of students validated the second activity.

3.2 Survey Results

The survey included 8 open-ended questions about this experience (experiment). Questions with responses (anonymous) are listed here in Table 3

Table 3. Overall Satisfaction.

Question	Totally Disagree	Disagree	No opinion	Agree	Fully Agree
The final mark reflects your work done	8,03%	19,20%	5,30%	22,44%	44,70%
The VARK Questionnaire was a good experience in PBL	12,54%	15,65%	9,80%	16,78%	45,23%
Teachers' assessment is more reliable	15,67%	51,61%	8,93%	12,45%	11,34%
I feel that I can do better next time	7,38%	2,57%	10,58%	32,06%	45,20%
The rules and steps of the workshops have been clearly explained by your teacher	7,82%	12,01%	9,23%	11,81%	40,87%
Are you satisfied with the results of your preferred learning style?	8,03%	16,06%	4,23%	45,81%	25,87%
Did you enjoy the experience?	3,04%	10,58%	4,27%	15,81%	66,33%

According to Table 3, we found out that about 81% are satisfied this experience. 45% are totally agree with the VARK experience in PBL. Only 70% said that they agree with the result of VARK questionnaire and 66% are satisfied with their final marks. Only 51% think that the rules and instructions were clear.

We list below some comments extracted from our survey:

"We're glad to have experienced this"

"Further tutorials and details about work needed"

"Dispose more clear videos with explanation, more explanations from my tutor"

"Keep our team with a selected learning style in case of randomness, I enjoyed this experience"

"I think that we must apply the Vark model of learning style in all of our courses and project"

As it was our first experience, we can understand the different opinions of several students. For next year, we have a number of things in mind in order to improve this experience. We propose to plan more training sessions for our team of tutors, to have some videos on Moodle to explain each stage, whether in each activity. The course materials available on Moodle should also be improved.

The survey showed that students can be encouraged to reflect critically on their own learning and performance by tailoring course materials to take account of their learning styles. It also helps them become more aware of their weaknesses and strengths.

4 Discussions

When we visualise the work of a team on a problem situation in which they are divided according to the nature of their learning style, we have noticed the following points:

Visual learners: They take notes, underline or highlight key points and sketch during lectures or discussions.

Auditory learners (Aural): Class discussions and verbal activities are enjoyed by auditory learners.

Reading and Writing learners: they highlight key points, taking notes, and summarize information which helps them process and retain the material;

Kinesthetic Learners: they enjoy the practical examples or stimulations. It is more difficult for them to grasp a theoretical situation or an abstract concept.

On the other hand, we have noticed that the distribution of preferences according to gender is as follows in Table 1 so the learning style is influenced by gender factor. Kinesthetic is the most influential learning style for male students, while for female, visual is the most significant learning style.

5 Conclusion

The term learning styles refers to the view that different people learn information in different ways. Understanding different learning styles and using the VARK model can greatly improve the effectiveness of your teaching. By recognising and responding to the different learning preferences of your students, you can create inclusive and engaging learning environments that promote meaningful understanding and retention of content. Every student has these different learning preferences, so it's important to take them into account to unlock their potential. The appropriate learning style model can help students to learn and understand learning approach, help to enhance self-strength and identify situations that can help towards the effectiveness of learning (Morrow, 2011). Understanding a good learning style has a number of positive effects for both teachers and students. A good understanding of a learning style will enable the teacher to explain the learning strategies that appeal to students according to their preferences. Teachers, in turn, can plan and implement appropriate teaching strategies in a way that students can easily understand. Teachers can play a role in helping pupils to explore learning strategies that suit them and are effective for them.

While the results are encouraging, we are of the opinion that some adjustments should be made in order to improve the overall experience. We will discuss the hybrid learning styles in the next step. We may find students who are both auditory and kinaesthetic, and others who are both visual and kinaesthetic, etc. This point will be explored in a future paper.

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